

SPECTROSCOPIC INVESTIGATION OF POLY-N-VINYLPYRROLIDONE MODIFIED MAGNETITE NANOPARTICLES ADDED CONCRETE

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Abstract

In the presented research, the nature of the chemical interactions formed by simultaneously introducing poly-N-vinylpyrrolidone (PVPr) and magnetite nanoparticles into the composition of the cement has been studied. For this purpose, concrete samples were prepared by filling cement with 1% PVPr and 1-2% magnetite nanoparticles at a water/cement ratio of 0.5. FTIR and XRD spectra of the obtained concrete samples were comparatively analyzed. It has been determined that the PVPr macromolecule forms coordination bonds with di-, tri-, Ca, and Al silicates in the cement. In the cement paste containing 1% and 2% Fe₃O₄ magnetite nanoparticles with PVPr, the absorption band associated with carbonyl shifted chemically from 1646 cm⁻¹ to 1653 cm⁻¹. It has been showed that magnetite nanoparticles interact chemically with both PVPr and water molecules present in the cement composition. The addition of PVPr-coated magnetite nanoparticles to the concrete composition results in a decrease in the intensity and shifting of peaks characteristic to concrete in XRD. As a result of the inclusion of magnetite nanoparticles into the structure, new low-intensity XRD patterns are observed at $2\theta = (30.17^\circ), (43.31^\circ), (54.61^\circ)$ and (62.75°) . These changes proved that magnetite nanoparticles entered into chemical interaction with Ca and Al di-, trisilicates in cement.

Keywords: poly-N-vinylpyrrolidone, magnetite nanoparticles, cement concrete, FTIR characterization, XRD characterization.

Introduction

In recent decades, the technology of concrete production with various additives has been developing rapidly[1]. In order to obtain the desired properties in concrete, water-soluble polymers, fibers, polymer dispersions and dispersed powders are added to the cement paste as dopants[2,3].

It is known that superabsorbent polymers (SAP) can absorb and retain large amounts of water by increasing their volume[4]. They are applied in various fields such as medicine[5,6], agriculture[7], and the food industry[8]. In recent years, they have been frequently used as repairing agents[10,11] for filling micro-cracks in cement-based materials[9]. SAPs on the surface of the cement coating can absorb water on the surface of micro-cracks, preventing the penetration of leachate by swelling[12]. The application of smart polymers in concrete mixtures gives them an advantage in the cementation of oil wells and the sealing of mud zones in the oil industry. Calcium ions in cement products reduce the water absorption capacity of acrylic acid-based polymers, preventing the formation of large masses[13]. pH-sensitive polymers with high absorption capacity in formation water can be a good choice for cementing oil wells[14]. Cement composites sometimes have disadvantages such as low splitting strength, poor resistance to deformation and susceptibility to cracking[15]. The creation of new composite concrete for modern engineers and concrete technologists is a genuine challenge, not only to provide mechanical properties but also to ensure other physico-chemical

characteristics, especially for structures exposed to aggressive environments. From this point of view, researches are being conducted in the direction of obtaining high-performance and multi-functional cement composites with excellent mechanical properties, durability and structural material, which are easy to produce[16,17].

It is known that nanoparticles, due to their unique physico-chemical properties, improve most of its properties by changing the microstructure of cement[18]. Si, Al, Ti, ZnO, TiO₂ nanoparticles were included in the cement composition in the researches[19-21]. Iron oxides (nano-Fe₂O₃ and nano-Fe₃O₄) specifically belong to this group of nanomaterials [22,23].

Concrete with added Fe₃O₄ magnetite nanoparticles has been obtained, and it has been determined that it exhibits lower water absorption capacity and higher tensile strength compared to ZrO₂, Al₂O₃, and TiO₂ nanoparticles[25,26]. Additionally, it has been observed that the addition of a small percentage of nano-magnetite to the cement paste enhances its compressive strength throughout all stages of the hydration process [27,28]. Research has shown that the incorporation of nanoparticles into cement results in significant improvements in the microstructures of cement composites [22,23]. The effect of nanoparticles is determined by their location in the microstructure[24].

In this study, cement paste modified with 1% (by mass) poly-N-vinylpyrrolidone (PVPr) was further supplemented with 1.0 and 2.0% (w/w) magnetite nanoparticles characterized by dimensions ranging from

30-50 nm. Their structures were analyzed using FTIR and X-ray diffraction spectroscopy methods. Characterization aims to determine the type of chemical interaction of the polymer and magnetite nanoparticles with cement components. Additionally, it aimed to identify the functional groups involved in the composite structure and delineate the spatial arrangement of macromolecular chains and nanoparticles within the concrete formulations.

Experimental

Materials

In the preparation of the concrete mixtures, G-class Portland cement (API Specification 10A-2011) intended for wellbore plugging, high average molecular weight PVPr (CAS 9003-39-8, $M_n=1.3 \times 10^6$), and distilled water were used. The predominant oxides in the composition of the cement are as follows: CaO 62.4%, SiO₂ 20.7%, Al₂O₃ 5.2%, MgO $\leq 1.24\%$, and Fe₂O₃ 4.3%. The composition of silicates comprises 59.2% C₃S, 2.18% C₃A, 16.75% C₄AF, and 9.16% C₂S, where C represents calcium, S represents silicate, A represents aluminum, and F represents ferrite. Iron chloride salts of both II and III valence states were utilized for the synthesis of magnetite nanoparticles, followed by their conversion to hydroxide form using a 25% NH₄OH solution.

Sample Preparation

The mixture of tamponage cement with water was prepared at a water/cement ratio of 0.5. PVPr constituted 1.0% of the dry mass of the cement it was added to. For the preparation of PVPr/Fe₃O₄ modified concrete samples, polymer/magnetite nanoparticles were initially synthesized following the method[29]. The preparation of concrete samples with 1.0 and 2.0% PVPr/Fe₃O₄ in the mass of the cement was carried out as follows: First, a 0.5-1.0 wt% PVPr/Fe₃O₄ mixture

was dispersed in 25 ml distilled water and stirred for 2 hours. The resulting solution was then added to 50 wt% Portland cement in a mixer. The mixture was poured into cylindrical molds and allowed to set for 24 hours. After one day, the samples were removed from the molds, dried at 30°C for 48 hours, and then pulverized for X-ray and IR spectroscopic analyses.

Characterization

The nature of the chemical interaction between macromolecules and cement particles in simple cement paste, also PVPr and PVPr/Fe₃O₄ nanoparticle-added samples was identified using Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy (Nicolet FT-IR Avatar 360). The crystalline phase in cement paste, PVPr, and PVPr/Fe₃O₄-containing concrete samples was investigated using X-ray diffractometry on an X' Pert-Pro MPD diffractometer (Cu-K α source, $k=0.15405$ nm).

Result And Discussion

It is known that concrete possesses a rigid structure primarily composed of calcium and aluminum silicates formed through ion interaction. The composition of hydrated cement differs to some extent from dry cement powder. In hydrated cement, the hydroxide forms of di- and tri-calcium and aluminum silicates are also present. During our research, serial samples were prepared to evaluate the chemical involvement of PVPr-coated magnetite nanoparticles in the concrete structure. For comparison, X-ray spectra of hydrated cement, PVPr-containing concrete, and PVPr/Fe₃O₄-containing concrete stones were obtained. It is known that in the XRD spectrum of concrete prepared from cement[30] specific peaks are observed at $2\theta = (26.58^\circ), (29.55^\circ), (32.49^\circ), (34.12^\circ), (41.32^\circ), (47.23^\circ), (50.68^\circ),$ and (51.87°) for di- and tri-calcium silicates, as well as calcium-aluminum silicates (Figure 1).

Fig 1. XRD diffractogram of the control concrete sample after 28 days of curing

To conduct comparative analyses, different concrete samples were prepared. X-ray analyses of concrete stones with PVPr and PVPr/Fe₃O₄ were conducted

to determine the function of both the polymer and magnetite nanoparticles in the structure. Notably, concrete prepared with 1% PVPr incorporation into the cement (Figure 2) displays subtly differentiated XRD patterns.

Fig 2. XRD diffractogram of concrete stone with 1% PVPr after 28 days

PVPr is an amorphous substance, and due to its 1% composition, it does not cause distinct separate peaks in the X-ray spectrum [31]. However, because the polymer interacts with Ca-Al silicates in the cement, it may lead to a decrease in the intensity or a shift of certain lines at specific 2θ values. Shifts at $2\theta =$

(39.32°), (43.42°), and (54.62°) are observed. At $2\theta =$ (56-58°), the formation of a second line indicates the immobilization of PVPr in the cement structure. After filling the concrete with both PVPr and magnetite nanoparticles, the XRD spectrum was examined (Figure 3).

Fig 3. XRD diffractogram of concrete stone filled with 1% Fe₃O₄/PVPr after 28 days

The characteristic peaks of iron oxide in the X-ray spectrum are observed at $2\theta =$ (30.17°), (43.31°), (54.61°), and (62.75°) with very low intensity. To con-

firm that these observed peaks are attributed to magnetite nanoparticles, concrete samples with doubled quantities of nanoparticles were prepared, and X-ray spectra were obtained (Figure 4).

Fig 4. XRD diffractogram of concrete sample filled with 2% Fe_3O_4 /PVPr after 28 days.

It has been determined that an increase in the quantity of magnetite nanoparticles in the composition of concrete leads to a clearer delineation of characteristic peaks and a discernible increase in their intensity in the X-ray spectrum. Moreover, the harder crystal structure of magnetite nanoparticles strengthens the X-ray spectrum of concrete even further. It is known that the iron atoms in magnetite nanoparticles are not in ionic form but rather comprise particles ranging in size between 30-45 nm. Observing these characteristic peaks

at 2θ where magnetite nanoparticles are expected indicates that the size of the nanoparticles remains unchanged in the concrete. Furthermore, the arrangement of magnetite nanoparticles in the concrete, maintaining both physical and chemical states, contributes to enhancing certain properties of concrete. To better understand the chemical position of magnetite nanoparticles, concrete stone samples were prepared with the participation of iron salts in cement paste and compared with polymer participation (Figure 5).

Fig 5. XRD diffractogram of 1% PVPr/concrete filled with 0.1% $FeCl_3$ and 0.1% $FeCl_2$ after 28 days.

It has been determined that the addition of iron ions significantly affects the hydration and hardening processes of cement. Metal ions hinder the hydration of calcium and aluminum silicates in the concrete, resulting in the formation of a rigid structure. This effect is visually apparent on the surface of concrete (Figure 6). According to XRD results, the decrease in intensity of

peaks at $2\theta = (29.7^\circ), (34.45^\circ), (39.69^\circ), (47.88^\circ),$ and (51.27°) is associated with a change in the characteristic crystal structure of pure concrete. Fe(II) and Fe(III) ions manifest as minor yet discernible lines with low intensity at $2\theta = (43.47^\circ)$ and (51.95°) in the X-ray spectrum.

Fig 6. Concrete samples filled with magnetite nanoparticles PVPr and Fe^{2+}/Fe^{3+} salts after 28 days of curing.

X-ray analyses indicate that the addition of 1% PVPr does not affect the crystal structure of concrete. On the contrary, it ensures coordination between calcium and aluminum silicates, providing long-distance connectivity in the structure. The introduction of magnetite nanoparticles along with the polymer into the

concrete further strengthens the structure, filling certain voids in the process. The type of chemical bonds formed between particles was determined using the FTIR method. Initially, the FTIR spectrum of control concrete was obtained (Figure 7).

Fig 7. FTIR spectrum of concrete prepared with a water-to-cement ratio of 0.5 cured in 28 days.

The characteristic peaks in the FTIR spectrum of hydrated cement and the relationships and bonds in the corresponding functional groups depicted in Figure 7. The introduction of PVPr macromolecules into the concrete composition leads to the observation of specific peaks related to the polymer in certain regions. Additionally, the chemical interaction of PVPr functional groups with the elements in the cement induces chemical shifts in some regions characteristic of concrete (Figure 8). It is known that characteristic peaks for PVPr in the FTIR spectrum are related to the carbonyl

(>C=O) and hydroxyl (-OH) groups in the regions of 1646 and 3450 cm^{-1} , respectively [32]. Furthermore, at 2950 cm^{-1} , the asymmetric stretching of CH_2 in pyrrolidone cycles is observed, and at 2922 cm^{-1} , the vibrations of CH_2 in the polymer chain are detected. Peaks at 1286 cm^{-1} represent the vibrational bending of CH_2 attached to C-N [33]. Although new peaks with different intensities are not observed in the FTIR spectrum of PVPr-concrete, small variations in absorption bands are noticed.

Fig 8. FTIR spectrum of concrete containing 1% PVPr cured in 28 days.

Based on the FTIR results of PVPr-containing concrete, the polymer has participated in active chemical interactions with silicates and has been immobilized in the concrete matrices along with metal silicates. The main chemical interaction relies on the carbonyl groups in PVPr. Specifically, the carbonyl group at 1646 cm^{-1} , characteristic for pure PVPr, chemically shifts to the region around 1653 cm^{-1} in the concrete. This indicates chemical interactions with some silicates in the concrete, suggesting a complex chemical reaction. All

these observations support the conclusion that PVPr macromolecules immobilized in concrete matrices with silicates, and similar results encountered in research [34].

The addition of PVPr-coated magnetite nanoparticles to the concrete composition results in the adsorption bands related to oxides in the FTIR spectrum, as shown in Figure 9.

Fig 9. FTIR spectrum of concrete containing 1% PVPr/ Fe_3O_4 magnetite nanoparticles cured in 28 days.

As seen in Figure 9, the characteristic absorption band of magnetite nanoparticles is observed in the 541 cm^{-1} region, while the peak corresponding to the carbonyl group in PVPr, which is actively involved in chemical interaction with Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles, undergoes chemical shifting up to the 1635 cm^{-1} region. In other regions, chemical shifts are minimal, indicating relatively passive chemical interaction with silicates in the cement. This proves that the magnetite nanoparticles exhibit a more active chemical interaction with PVPr within the concrete structure, while their interaction with cement components appears to be relatively

passive. This can be explained by the more rapid mutual interaction of Ca and Al silicates with water molecules and PVPr during the hydration stage of cement. Furthermore, considering that magnetite nanoparticles are mixed with cement powder in complex with PVPr macromolecules, it can be understood that iron oxide molecules are more densely coordinated around the polymer.

To determine the chemical interaction of magnetite nanoparticles with PVPr or silicates, concrete specimens were prepared with the participation of iron salts and polymer, and FTIR spectra were obtained (Figure 10).

Fig 10. FTIR spectrum of 1% PVPr/concrete filled with 0.1% FeCl_3 and 0.1% FeCl_2 after 28 days.

It has been determined that the characteristic band at 540 cm^{-1} for magnetite nanoparticles does not observed in the spectrum. However, the active complexation of iron ions with PVPr leads to the appearance of the absorption band associated with carbonyl in a different region compared to the polymer. The results suggest that PVPr chains serve as a bridge between cement

particles and magnetite nanoparticles in the concrete. This role of magnetite nanoparticles in such an interaction has observed in various research studies [35]. The chemical interaction of iron ions with silicates in the cement also becomes apparent in the FTIR spectrum of the concrete/Fe salt sample in the absence of polymers (Figure 11).

Fig 11. FTIR spectrum of concrete filled with 0.1% $FeCl_3$ and 0.1% $FeCl_2$ after 28 days.

Despite the iron ions constituting only 0.1% of the mass of the cement, their active interaction with silicates is evident in the tracking of characteristic lines in the spectrum. The active chemical interaction of iron ions with silicates has led to a sharp decrease in the intensity of the characteristic peak at 964 cm^{-1} corresponding to Si-O. On the other hand, the passive participation of PVPr in the composition showed by the shift of the broad band characteristic of -OH groups to the region of $3400\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Based on the comparative analysis of FTIR spectra, the addition of PVPr-coated magnetite nanoparticles to the cement paste does not hinder the hydration process. The homogeneous distribution of polymer and iron oxides in the structure ensures the distribution of PVPr-silicate and PVPr/ Fe_3O_4 /silicate interactions not only locally but throughout the entire volume and surface. This confirms that mechanical properties are maintained equally in all directions throughout the concrete. Research studies often encounter enhanced mechanical properties in polymer-cement systems attributed to the reinforcement of the matrix by polymer macromolecular chains [36].

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